

An Assessment of Indoor Household in Akure Ondo State

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Abstract

Worldwide deaths in 2012 exceeded 4 million, according to the World Health Organization (WHO). This was brought on by particulate matter (PM) with a diameter of 2.5 microns, one of the indoor culprits. By giving individualized information on indoor concentrations in real-time, the introduction of low-cost PM measuring systems encourages people to take action. A group of researchers from ENEA, the Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy, and the Environment, created and tested SentinAir, the inexpensive sensor utilized in this study. Brindisi Research Center's Sustainable Development Department is located in Italy. It tracks temperature, relative humidity, NO₂, SO₂, CO₂, O₃, and particle matter (1, 2.5, and 10). The sensor was placed in a typical indoor household space (the kitchen) with the objective of analyzing all variables over the course of thirty (30) days as a preliminary study assessment. The sensor's correct operation was properly followed. The results (mean) (64%) included PM₁ (17.80 µg/m³), PM_{2.5} (25.21 µg/m³), PM₁₀ (27.61 µg/m³), CO₂ (419.7 ppm), O₃ (24.75 ppb), NO₂ (66.52 ppb), SO₂ (48.04 ppb), temperature (34.1 °C), and humidity. It was found that PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ were well under the 24 h guideline limits of 25 and 50 µg/m³, respectively, once those data were compared to those of the WHO. PM_{2.5}, however, can be dangerous. The contaminants were significantly influenced by the temperature and humidity. The biggest increase in PM in the kitchen was brought on by frying and baking food. It is advised that this low-cost PM sensor be integrated into an indoor air-quality monitoring network in order to enable people to assess their individual exposure because the data is reproducible.

Keywords: Indoor air; Particulate matter; Sensor network, Low-cost particulate matter sensor

Received: 15/01/2021

Accepted: 24/03/2021

Introduction

Two of the top ten global issues that increase morbidity and mortality are pollution, both indoor and outdoor [1]. Nowadays, people spend 90% of their time indoors, exposing themselves to indoor air pollutants for a longer period of time than people who spend most of their time outside [2]. Therefore, it is crucial to distinguish and quantify indoor air in order to comprehend its components and, in the case of a potentially harmful concentration level of chemical species hazardous to people's health, identify factors at fault (direct or indirect sources of pollutants) [3]. Indoor exposure was linked to a number of health problems in 2016 including respiratory ailments and 3.8 million deaths globally [4]. Carbon dioxide (CO₂), carbon monoxide (CO), formaldehyde (CH₂O), total volatile organic compounds (VOC), particle matter (PM), and, at the microbiological level, bacteria and fungi are pollutants that are frequently assessed in indoor air quality (IAQ) monitoring [5].

Low-cost sensors have developed as a cost-effective substitute for precision equipment used in long-term environmental monitoring in recent years [6–8]. Low-cost air pollution sensors exhibit flaws and inconsistencies in terms of accuracy, consistency, and long-term reliability [7, 9]. On the other hand, inexpensive sensors allow for the mobilization of a significantly greater number of units, and due to their portability and tiny size, they are ideal for usage in micro-environments where conventional technology would be too challenging. Low-cost sensors may be particularly helpful for detecting indoor air pollution because of the latter attribute.

The low-cost SentinAir sensor is exclusive to this area of Africa [10]. Compared to many cheap sensors on the market, it examines more parameters (pollutants and weather factors). Therefore, when compared to other pieces of equipment, this one definitely outperforms them. The primary goal of this study is to assess the pollutants (PM₁, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, CO₂, O₃, NO₂, and SO₂) as well as the environmental factors (temperature and relative humidity – RH) of the ideal indoor environment.

Materials and Methods

Oba-Ile, located in Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria (latitude/longitude: 7 16 04.4 N 5 14 29.1 E), is the monitoring station used in this study. The building is surrounded by gravel roads in a residential area (Figure 1). There haven't been any significant point sources of emissions in the neighborhood that are known.

In this investigation, SentinAir (Figure 2), a device created and developed for data collection from various instruments, sensors, or devices [11, 12], was used. The sensor protocol was followed to the letter. For 32 days, the sensor was checked for the presence of PM₁, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂, SO₂, CO₂, O₃, temperature, and relative

humidity. 4 meters above ground, the sensor box was positioned on a rack. The sensor package was roughly 6 meters distant from the local lane of traffic because the only thing separating the house from the road was a concrete wall.

After the monitoring period was up, the sensor data was examined and evaluated. The basic description, the Pearson sample correlation coefficient (r), the matrix plot, and the boxplot were all computed using the Minitab version.

Fig. 1. The Goggle Map of the Study Location

Fig. 2. The figure shows (a) the complete set-up of the low-cost sensor, and (b) the inlet of the sensor showing the power charger,

Results and Discussion

Table 1. The Basic Description

Parameters	PM ₁	PM _{2.5}	PM ₁₀	SO ₂	NO ₂	O ₃	CO ₂
Mean	17.8	25.2	27.6	48.8	66.5	24.8	419.72
Std Dev.	5.3	7.8	11.7	23.0	45.0	9.2	102.0
Minimum	1.0	2.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	303.60
Maximum	34.0	51.0	161.0	79.0	282.0	79.0	1003.30
Skewness	-0.3	-0.2	3.2	-1.2	1.9	0.5	2.43
Kurtosis	0.1	-0.2	32.8	0.1	4.6	5.0	6.78
Ist Quartile	15.0	21.0	22.0	43.0	40.0	20.5	361.45
3 rd Quartile	21.0	31.0	32.5	64.0	79.0	30.0	436.25

Units: PM₁ - µg/m³, PM_{2.5} - µg/m³, PM₁₀ - µg/m³, SO₂ - ppb, NO₂ - ppb, O₃ - ppb

Table 2. The Correlation Coefficients of the Pollutants and the meteorological Parameters

	Temp	RH	NO ₂	O ₃	SO ₂	PM ₁	PM _{2.5}	PM ₁₀	CO ₂
Temp	1								
RH	-0.77	1							
NO ₂	-0.31	0.39	1						
O ₃	0.24	-0.14	0.63	1					
SO ₂	0.66	-0.47	-0.30	0.28	1				
PM ₁	0.12	-0.15	0.20	0.30	0.01	1			
PM _{2.5}	0.12	-0.15	0.19	0.30	0.01	0.99	1		
PM ₁₀	0.10	-0.16	0.18	0.28	0.01	0.94	0.97	1	
CO ₂	-0.13	0.32	0.50	0.61	0.27	0.06	0.07	0.05	1

Table 1 displays a brief explanation of the parameters. Hourly observations were used to average daily mean concentrations, and daily and monthly mean concentrations were used to average monthly mean concentrations. Pollutant mean values are as follows: PM₁ (17.80 µg/m³), PM_{2.5} (25.21 µg/m³), PM₁₀ (27.61 µg/m³), CO₂ (419.72 ppm), O₃ (24.75 ppb), NO₂ (66.52 ppb), SO₂ (48.04 ppb). In comparison to WHO guidelines, PM₁, PM_{2.5} (25 µg/m³ - 24 h mean), PM₁₀ (50 µg/m³ - 24 h mean), SO₂ (20 µg/m³ - 24 h mean), NO₂ (200 µg/m³ - 1h mean), and O₃ (100 µg/m³ - 8h mean) were higher. The highest levels of O₃, NO₂, and CO₂ are 79, 282, and 1003.3 ppb, respectively. The highest values obtained are two and three times higher, respectively, when PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ levels are assessed and compared. Cooking, heating, and lighting in homes that use non-renewable energy sources like old cooking utensils or open flames exposes residents to indoor and outdoor pollution. This demonstrates unequivocally that lung cancer, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, cardiovascular disease, and acute respiratory diseases are all at increased risk due to air pollution [13]. Additionally, there is a twofold increase in SO₂ concentration.

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ISSN: 1597 - 9928. Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

According to the World Health Organization, a SO₂ level of 500 µg/m³ should not be exceeded for average periods of 10 minutes due to health effects associated with respiratory tract inflammation, which causes coughing, mucus secretion, aggravation of asthma and chronic bronchitis, and increases susceptibility to breathing problems. Short-term NO₂ concentrations over 200 µg/m³ are hazardous gases that irritate the airways. The primary source of nitrate airborne particles is NO₂, which also significantly contributes to PM_{2.5} and, when exposed to UV light, ozone.

The variable correlations between the various parameters are listed in Table 2. According to the table, there are moderate relationships ($r=-0.77$) between temperature, RH ($r=-0.77$), and SO₂ ($r=0.66$); however, RH has relation ($r=0.32-0.39$) with all of the parameters. NO₂ has weak relationships with O₃ and CO₂ ($r=0.63$ and 0.50 , respectively). SO₂ has low correlations ($r=0.01-0.27$) with PM₁, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀. The findings demonstrate significant relationship between PMs ($r=0.94-0.97$), but poor relationships between PMs and CO₂ ($r=0.05-0.07$). Table 2 shows that the correlation between pollution concentrations and climatic parameters is weaker and more moderately significant. At the 0.05 level, a link between global radiation and PM might be considered positive. Secondary particulate matter is created in the atmosphere as a result of photochemical reactions fueled by global radiation [14]. The link between RH and PM_{2.5} shows that RH has no impact on the scavenging of tiny particles. The positive association between temperature and O₃ shows that higher temperatures are advantageous for photochemical processes [15].

Fig. 3. The Boxplot of the pollutants and the meteorological parameters

In all of the branches that were determined using box and whisker plots, Figure 3 shows the information levels in terms of the median, minimum, and maximum. This study illustrates how regular air pollution concentrations might vary. The allocation of the underlying data is essentially sketched out in the box graphic. The boxplot displays the fluctuations in the amounts of common pollutants. Significant differences in pollutant representation suggest that different activities within the building, particularly in the kitchen, result in different levels of pollution.

Conclusion

This study, which used a cheap sensor, was carried out inside a housing complex and is the subject of this article. For 32 days, the sensor-appropriate technique was used to detect meteorological conditions (temperature and relative humidity), as well as pollutants (PM₁, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, CO₂, SO₂, NO₂, and O₃). The highest values obtained are two and three times higher, respectively than the WHO standards, while the mean PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ levels have been reported to be within those limits for 24 hours. The SO₂ levels are also twice as high. The World Health Organization advises against exposure to SO₂ levels of more than 500 µg/m³ for longer than 10 minutes on average. The highest levels of O₃, NO₂, and CO₂ are, respectively, 79, 282, and 1003.3 ppb. The home is exposed to pollutants from both inside and outside when polluting fuels are burned for cooking, heating, and lighting on open flames or using traditional kitchen appliances. This suggests a higher risk of illnesses linked to air pollution, including lung cancer, cardiovascular disease, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, and acute lower respiratory infections. The boxplot demonstrates that the portrayal of pollutants varies noticeably, indicating that the pollutants vary based on kitchen activity.

Acknowledgements

The sensor was provided by Dr. Suriano and Prof. Penza of the Department of Sustainable Development, Brindisi Research Center, Italy, which is part of ENEA, the Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy, and the Environment. Also, we wish to thank Dr. F.O. Abulude of Environmental and Sustainable Group (ESRG), Science and Education Development Institute, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria for the assistance provided

Conflict of Interest

There are no conflict interest

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